

Strongly Hopfian Objets and Strongly Cohopfian Objets in the Categories of
 $AGr(A-Mod)$ and $COMP(AGr(A-Mod))$

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Abstract

1. Let M be a graded left A -module and M_* the associate complex of M . Then :
 - (a) If M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian) then M_* is strongly hopfian (resp. strongly cohopfian) ;
 - (b) If M_* is strongly hopfian (resp. cohopfian), then M_* is hopfian (resp. cohopfian) ;
2. Let M be a graded left A -module, M_* the associate complex of M , N a submodule of M , and N_* fully invariant subcomplex of M_* . Then :
If N_* and M_*/N_* strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian.
3. Let M a graded left A -module, N a submodule of M and M_* the associate complex of M . Then :
 - (a) if all subcomplex of M_* is cohopfian, then M_* is cohopfian.
 - (b) if M_*/N_* is strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian

Keywords :

Graded rings, graded module, category, sequence complex, chains complex, strongly cohopfian objects, and strongly hopfian object.

1 Introduction

In this paper, the ring A is supposed to be associative, unitary and not necessarily commutative, every left A -module is unifere.

The aim of this article is to study the strongly hopfian and strongly cohopfian objects in the category of graded left A -modules denoted $AGr(A-Mod)$ and in the category of associated complex of graded left A -modules denoted $COMP(AGr(A-Mod))$. In particular we give conditions over M_* and N_* such that M_*/N_* be strongly cohopfian (respectively strongly hopfian) and conditions over M_*/N_* and N_* such that M_* be strongly hopfian.

We define $AGr(A-Mod)$ and $COMP(AGr(A-Mod))$:

1. The category of graded of left A -modules denoted $AGr(A - Mod)$ where :
 - (a) The objects are the graded left A -modules ;
 - (b) The morphisms are the graded morphisms..
2. the category of complexes associate of graded left A -modules denoted $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ where
 - (a) the objects are the complex sequences associated to a left A -modules ;
 - (b) the morphisms are the complex chains associated to a graded morphisms.

The principal results of this article are given in the third and forth section, here are the results :

1. Let M be a graded left A -module and M_* the associate complex of M . Then :
 - (a) If M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian) then M_* is strongly hopfian (resp. strongly cohopfian) ;
 - (b) If M_* is strongly hopfian (resp. cohopfian), then M_* is hopfian (resp. cohopfian) ;
2. Let M be a graded left A -module, M_* the associate complex of M , N a submodule of M , and N_* fully invariant subcomplex of M_* . Then :
If N_* and M_*/N_* strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian.
3. Let M a graded left A -module, N a submodule of M and M_* the associate complex of M . Then :
 - (a) if all subcomplex of M_* is cohopfian, then M_* is cohopfian.
 - (b) if M_*/N_* is strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian

2 Reminder and preliminary results

Définition 2.1

Let A be a ring, we say that A is a graded ring if there exists a family $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of additive subgroup of A such that

1. $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$;
2. $A_n \cdot A_m \subset A_{n+m}, \forall n, m \in \mathbb{Z}$.

In all that follows, A and M are supposed unitary.

Remarque 2.1

Let A be a graded ring.

We say that A is positively graded if $A_n = 0, \forall n < 0$.

Définition 2.2

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring and M be a left A -module, we say that M is a graded left A -module if there exists a suite $(M_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of sub-group of M such that :

1. $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$;
2. $A_n \cdot M_d \subset M_{n+d}, \forall n, d \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Définition 2.3

Lets $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ be a graded left A -module and N is a sub-module of M , then we say that N is a graded sub-module of M , if $\forall x = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} x_n \in N$, with $x_n \in M_n$, then $x_n \in N, \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Proposition 2.1

Lets $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring and $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ is graded left A -module, then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ fixed, we have

$$M(n) = \bigoplus_{k \geq n} M_k = \bigoplus_{k \in \mathbb{N}} M_{n+k}$$

is a graded sub-module of M and we have the descendant sequence :

$$\dots M(n+2) \subset M(n+1) \subset M(n) \subset \dots$$

Proof

For all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ fixed, $M(n) = \bigoplus_{k \geq n} M_k$ is a sub-group of M and

$$A_s \cdot M(n)_k = A_s \cdot M_{n+k} \subset M_{n+k+s} = M_{n+(k+s)} = M(n)_{k+s}.$$

In the other hand, it suffices to remark that

$$M(n) = \bigoplus_{k \geq n} M_k = M_n \bigoplus M(n+1) = \bigoplus_{k \in \mathbb{N}} M_k.$$

Hence $M(n+1) \subset M(n)$. Thus

$$\dots M(n+2) \subset M(n+1) \subset M(n) \subset \dots$$

Définition 2.4

Lets $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ and $N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ two graded left A -modules and $f : M \rightarrow N$ is a morphism of left A -modules, then we say that f is a graded morphism if for any $m \in M_s$ then $f(m) \in N_{s+k}$.

Théorème et Définition 2.1

Let A be a graded ring, then the following information :

1. The objects are the graded left A -modules ;
2. The morphisms are the graded morphisms..

constitute a category called the category of graded left A -module and which is denoted by $\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})\text{-Mod}$.

Proof

Lets M, N be two objects of $\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})$, then M and N are two graded left A -modules and :

1. $\text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(M, N) = \{ \text{Set of graded morphisms of } M \text{ to } N \}$;
2. The morphisms are the graded morphisms then we have :
 - (a) $\forall f \in \text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(M, N) ; \forall g \in \text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(N, P) ; \forall h \in \text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(P, Q)$ we have : $(h \circ g) \circ f = h \circ (g \circ f)$, because f, g, h are a morphisms of left A -modules and if $m \in M$, then $f(m) \in N$ then $g(f(m)) \in P$, Hence $g \circ f$ is a graded morphism.

(b) Let M be an object of $\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})$ then we have :

$$1_M : M \longrightarrow M$$

$$m \longmapsto m$$

1_M verifies $f \circ 1_M(m) = f(m), \forall m \in M$
 $\Rightarrow f \circ 1_M = f, \forall f \in \text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(M, N)$.
 Moreover $1_M \circ g(n) = 1_M(g(n)) = g(n), \forall n \in N$,
 thus $1_M \circ g = g \forall g \in \text{Hom}_{\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})}(N, M)$.

Thus $\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod})$ is a category.

Définition 2.5

A complex sequence $(C, d) : \dots \rightarrow C_{n+1} \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} C_n \xrightarrow{d_n} C_{n-1} \xrightarrow{d_{n-1}} \dots$ is a sequence of morphisms of A -modules satisfying $d_n \circ d_{n+1} = 0$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Définition 2.6

A complex chain $f : (C, d) \rightarrow (C', d')$ is a sequence of homomorphisms $(f_n : C_n \rightarrow C'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of A -modules making the following diagram commute :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} (C, d) : \dots & \longrightarrow & C_{n+1} & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & C_n & \xrightarrow{d_n} & C_{n-1} \longrightarrow \dots \\ & & f \downarrow & & f_{n+1} \downarrow & & f_n \downarrow & & f_{n-1} \downarrow \\ (C', d') : \dots & \longrightarrow & C'_{n+1} & \xrightarrow{d'_{n+1}} & C'_n & \xrightarrow{d'_n} & C'_{n-1} \longrightarrow \dots \end{array}$$

i.e $d'_{n+1} \circ f_{n+1} = f_n \circ d_{n+1}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Proposition et Définition 2.1

We called the category of complexes of A -modules and we denote $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$, the category whose :

1. The objects are the sequences complex;
2. The morphisms are the complex chains.

Proof

See [4]

Proposition 2.2

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring and $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ be a graded left A -module, then we have the following associate complex sequence M_* of a grade A -module $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$:

$$M_* : \dots \rightarrow M(n+1) \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} M(n) \xrightarrow{d_n} M(n-1) \rightarrow \dots$$

with $M(n) = \bigoplus_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} M_{n+k}$ and

$$d_n : M(n) \longrightarrow M(n-1)$$

$$x = y + z \longmapsto y$$

with $(y, z) \in M_n \times M(n+1)$.

Proof

We have $M(n) = \bigoplus_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} M_{n+k} = \bigoplus_{k \geq n} M_k = M_n \bigoplus M_{n+1}$ and

$$M(n-1) = M_{n-1} \bigoplus M(n) = M_{n-1} \bigoplus M_n \bigoplus M(n+1).$$

Let $x \in M(n)$, then it exists a unique $(y, z) \in M_n \times M(n+1)$ such that $x = y + z$.

Put

$$\begin{aligned} d_n : M(n) &\longrightarrow M(n-1) \\ x = y + z &\longmapsto y \end{aligned}$$

so $\text{Im}(d_n) = M_n$; on the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} d_{n-1} : M(n-1) &\longrightarrow M(n-2) \\ w = u + v &\longmapsto u \end{aligned}$$

with $(u, v) \in M_{n-1} \times M(n)$ so $\ker(d_{n-1}) = M(n)$ so $\text{Im}(d_n) \subset \ker(d_{n-1})$ so

$$d_{n-1} \circ d_n = 0$$

thus

$$M_* : \cdots \rightarrow M(n+1) \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} M(n) \xrightarrow{d_n} M(n-1) \rightarrow \cdots$$

is a complex sequence.

Proposition 2.3

Let M be a graded left A -module, N a graded submodule of M , M_* the complex associate to M and for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $N(n)$ is a submodule of $M(n)$. Then

$$N_* : \cdots \rightarrow N(n+1) \xrightarrow{\delta_{n+1}} N(n) \xrightarrow{\delta_n} N(n-1) \rightarrow \cdots \text{ with } d_n(x) = \delta_n(n)(x)$$

is a subcomplex of M_*

Proof

We have $\delta_n : N(n+1) \longrightarrow N(n)$

let $x, y \in N(n+1) : x = y$

then $d_n(x) = d_n(y)$

$\implies \delta_n(x) = \delta_n(y)$

\implies is well defined.

Let's calculate $\delta_n \circ \delta_{n+1}$

Let $x \in N(n+1)$, we have :

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_n \circ \delta_{n+1}(x) &= \delta_n(\delta_{n+1}(x)) \\ &= \delta_n(d_{n+1}(x)) = d_n(d_{n+1}(x)) = d_n \circ d_{n+1}(x) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\delta_n \circ \delta_{n+1} = 0$

hence N_* is a subcomplex of M_* .

Proposition 2.4

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ and $N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ are two graded left A -module $f : M \longrightarrow N$ is a graded morphism of a graded left A -modules, then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(n) : M(n) &\longrightarrow N(n) \\ m &\longmapsto f(n)(m) = f(m) \end{aligned}$$

is graded morphism of graded left A -modules.

Proof

We have $f : M \rightarrow N$ is graded morphism of graded left A -modules, and $M(n)$ is a sub-module of graded left A -module M then let $m \in M(n)$, so

$$m = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} m_{i+n} \implies f(n)(m) = f(m) = f\left(\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} m_{i+n}\right) = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} f(m_{i+n})$$

or $f(m_{i+n}) \in N_{i+n+k} = (N(n))_{i+k}$ thus f is graded morphism of a graded left A -modules.

Corollaire 2.1

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$ and $N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ are two graded left A -module $f : M \rightarrow N$ is a graded morphism of a graded left A -modules, then $f : M \rightarrow N(k)$ is graded morphism of graded left A -modules.

Proof

We have $f : M \rightarrow N$ is graded morphism of graded left A -modules, and $N(k)$ is a sub-module of graded left A -module N then let $m \in M$, so

$$m = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} m_i \implies f(m) = f\left(\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} m_i\right) = \sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} f(m_i)$$

or $f(m_i) \in N_{i+k} = (N(k))_i$ thus f is graded morphism of a graded left A -modules.

Proposition 2.5

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, $M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n$, $N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ are two graded left A -modules and $f : M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n \rightarrow N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ is a graded morphism of a graded A -modules, then we have the following associated chain complex f_* of graded morphism $f : M = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} M_n \rightarrow$

$N = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} N_n$ of a graded A -modules :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) \longrightarrow \dots \\ f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & f(n-1) \downarrow \\ N_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & N(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d'_{n+1}} & N(n) & \xrightarrow{d'_n} & N(n-1) \longrightarrow \dots \end{array}$$

Proof

Prove that for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$f(n) \circ d_{n+1} = d'_{n+1} \circ f(n+1).$$

Let $x \in M(n+1)$, then it exists the unique couple $(y, z) \in M_{n+1} \times M(n+2)$ such that $x = y + z$ so

$$(f(n) \circ d_{n+1})(x) = f(n)[d_{n+1}(x)] = f[d_{n+1}(x)] = f[y] = f(y)$$

and

$$(d'_{n+1} \circ f(n+1))(x) = d'_{n+1}[f(n+1)(x)] = d'_{n+1}[f(x)] = d'_{n+1}[f(y+z)] = d'_{n+1}[f(y)+f(z)] = f(y)$$

because $f(y) \in N_{n+1}$ and $f(z) \in N(n+2)$

$$\implies (f(n) \circ d_{n+1})(x) = (d'_{n+1} \circ f(n+1))(x), \quad \forall x \in M(n+1)$$

so

$$f(n) \circ d_{n+1} = d'_{n+1} \circ f(n+1)$$

thus f_* is a complex chain.

Théorème et Définition 2.2

Let $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ be a graded ring, then the following information :

1. The objects are the associated complex sequences of a graded left A -modules ;
2. The morphisms are the associate complex chains of a graded morphism of a graded left A -modules.

formed a category called the category of associate complex of a graded left A -modules and denoted by $\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$.

Proof

1. Lets M_* and N_* two complex sequences associated with graded left A -module M and N respectively.

Put $\text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M_*, N_*) =$ the class of complex chains associate to graded morphism of $M \rightarrow N$. Then $\text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M_*, N_*)$ is a set, because the class of complex chain of $M_* \rightarrow N_*$ of the category $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})(M_*, N_*)$ is a set (it suffices to remark also the class of graded of $M \rightarrow N$ is a set).

2. $\forall f_* \in \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M_*, N_*) ; g_* \in \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(N_*, P_*)$ and $h_* \in \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(P_*, Q_*)$ we have :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & \dots \\
 f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & \\
 N_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & N(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d'_{n+1}} & N(n) & \xrightarrow{d'_n} & \dots \\
 g_* \downarrow & & g(n+1) \downarrow & & g(n) \downarrow & & \\
 P_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & P(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d''_{n+1+k+r}} & P(n) & \xrightarrow{d''_{n+k+r}} & \dots \\
 h_* \downarrow & & h(n+1) \downarrow & & h(n) \downarrow & & \\
 Q_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & Q(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d'''_{n+1}} & Q(n) & \xrightarrow{d'''_n} & \dots
 \end{array}$$

So $(h_* \circ g_*) \circ f_* = h_* \circ (g_* \circ f_*)$;

3. Let M_* the object of $\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ we have :

$$1_{M_*} : M_* \longrightarrow M_*$$

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & \dots \\
 1_{M_*} \downarrow & & 1(n+1) \downarrow & & 1(n) \downarrow & & \\
 M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & \dots
 \end{array}$$

1_{M_*} verified $f_* \circ 1_{M_*} = f_* \quad \forall f_* \in \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M_*, N_*)$.

Furthermore $1_{M_*} \circ g_* = g_* \quad \forall g_* \in \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(N_*, M_*)$.

4. $\forall (M_*, N_*) \neq (M'_*, N'_*) \implies \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M_*, N_*) \neq \text{Hom}_{\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))}(M'_*, N'_*)$

Thus $\text{COMP}(\text{Gr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ is a category.

Remarque 2.2

$\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ is a subcategory of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$

Proposition et Définition 2.2

Let $(C, d) : \dots \rightarrow C_{n+1} \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} C_n \xrightarrow{d_n} C_{n-1} \rightarrow \dots$ be a complex sequence of left A -modules and (E_n) be a family of left A -modules such that for all n , E_n is a submodule of C_n . If $d_n(E_n) \subset E_{n-1}$, then the complex sequence of induced morphisms $(d_n : E_n \rightarrow E_{n-1})$ is complex sequence of left A -modules called subcomplex of C

Proof

Suppose that $\delta_n : E_n \rightarrow E_{n-1}$ the induced morphism of d_n , we show that δ_n is well defined.

Suppose that $x \in E_n$, hence $d_n(x) \in E_n$, then δ_n is well defined.

δ_n is a morphism, since it's composed of two morphisms.

Let's verify that $\delta_n \circ \delta_{n+1} = 0$

Let be $x \in E_{n+1}$, hence $\delta_{n+1}(x) = d_{n+1}(x) \in E_n$ and $\delta((d_{n+1})(x)) = d_n \circ d_{n+1}(x) = 0$, then $\delta_n \circ \delta_{n+1} = 0$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Proposition et Définition 2.3

Let C be a complex and E be a subcomplex of C . Suppose that $K = (K_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$, where $K_n = C_n/E_n$. Then K is a complex sequence called quotient complex of C by E and denoted C/E

Proof

See [13]

Théorème 2.1

let $(C, d), (C', d')$ two objects of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$ and $f : C \rightarrow C'$ be a complex chain. Then

f is a monomorphism of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$ if, and only, if $\ker f = 0$.

Proof

Suppose that f is a monomorphism of C into C' , hence $f \circ u = f \circ v \implies u = v$, then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $f_n \circ u_n = f_n \circ v_n \implies u_n = v_n$, so f_n is a monomorphism, thus $\ker f_n = 0$, hence $\ker f = 0$.

Reciprocally, suppose $\ker f = 0$, hence $\ker f$ is a zero complex, so each term is zero, thus f_n is a monomorphism of left A -modules then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ it gives if $f_n \circ u_n = f_n \circ v_n$ hence $u_n = v_n$, so $(f \circ u)_n = (f \circ v)_n \implies (u)_n = (v)_n$, finally, f is a monomorphism of complex chains

Théorème 2.2

let $(C, d), (C', d')$ two objects of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$ and $f : (C, d) \rightarrow (C', d')$ be a complex chain. Then

f is an epimorphism of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$ if, and only, if $\text{Im} f = C'$.

Proof

Suppose that f is an epimorphism of $\text{COMP}(A - \text{Mod})$, then $u \circ f = v \circ f \implies u = v$, hence for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $(u \circ f)_n = (v \circ f)_n \implies u_n = v_n$, f_n is an epimorphism of left A -modules, then $\text{Im} f_n = C'_n$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, so $\text{Im} f = C'$.

Reciprocally, suppose that $\text{Im} f = C'$, hence for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\text{Im} f_n = C'_n$, then f_n is an

epimorphism of left A -modules so for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $u_n \circ f_n = v_n \circ f_n$, then $(u \circ f)_n = (v \circ f_n) \implies u_n = v_n$ then f is an epimorphism of complex chains.

3 Strongly hopfian objects in the catégories $AGr(A - Mod)$ and $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$

Définitions 3.1

Let M_* be an object of $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \\ f_* \downarrow & & f^{(n+1)} \downarrow & & f^{(n)} \downarrow & & f^{(n-1)} \downarrow & & \\ M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \end{array}$$

We call $f_* \circ f_*$ the chain complex compounded of f_* by itself denoted f_*^2 .
 We also define $(f^2)_n = f_n \circ f_n$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.
 We also define f_*^k such that $f^k(n) = f(n) \circ f(n) \circ \dots \circ f(n)$, with k factors, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Proposition 3.1

Let M_* be an object of $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \\ f_* \downarrow & & f^{(n+1)} \downarrow & & f^{(n)} \downarrow & & f^{(n-1)} \downarrow & & \\ M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \end{array}$$

Given $\Delta^k(n+1) : \ker f^k(n+1) \longrightarrow \ker f^k(n)$
 $x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$
 where $f^k(n+1) = f(n+1) \circ f(n+1) \circ \dots \circ f(n+1)$, with k factors, then $\Delta^k(n+1)$ is the induced morphism by $\Delta^{k+1}(n+1)$.

Proof

Considering $\Delta^k(n+1) : \ker f^k(n+1) \longrightarrow \ker f^k(n)$
 $x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$
 and $\Delta^{k+1}(n+1) : \ker f^{k+1}(n+1) \longrightarrow \ker f^{k+1}(n)$
 $x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$
 We obtain $\ker f^k(n+1) \subset \ker f^{k+1}(n+1)$ and $\ker f^k(n) \subset \ker f^{k+1}(n)$, therefore $\Delta^k(n+1)$ is the induced by Δ^{k+1} .

Définitions 3.2

Let M_* be an object of $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \\ f_* \downarrow & & f^{(n+1)} \downarrow & & f^{(n)} \downarrow & & f^{(n-1)} \downarrow & & \\ M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \end{array}$$

Then the chain complex

$$(\ker f_*^k) : \dots \rightarrow \ker f^k(n+1) \xrightarrow{\Delta_{n+1}^k} \ker f^k(n) \xrightarrow{\Delta_n^k} \ker f^k(n-1) \xrightarrow{\Delta_{n-1}^k} \dots$$

is stationary if, and only if, it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that $(\ker f_*^{k_0}) = (\ker f_*^{k_0+s})$ for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proposition 3.2

Let M_* be an object of $\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \cdots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \cdots \\ & & f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & f(n-1) \downarrow \\ M_* : \cdots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \cdots \end{array}$$

Then $(\ker f_*^k)$ is stationary if, and only if, $(\ker f^k(n))$ stabilizes for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$

Proof

If $(\ker f_*^k)$ is stationary, then it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that $(\ker f_*^k) = (\ker f_*^{k+s})$, for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$, hence $\ker f^{k_0}(n) = \ker f^{k_0+s}(n)$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. This implies that $(\ker f^k(n))$ stabilizes for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Reciprocally, assume that $(\ker f^k(n))$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, then it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$ then $\ker f^{k_0}(n) = \ker f^{k_0+s}(n)$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

So $(\ker f_*^k)$ is stationary for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$

Définitions 3.3

Let M_* be an object of $\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* . M_* is said to be strongly hopfian, if for any endomorphism f_* of M_* , $(\ker f_*^k)$ is stationary.

Théorème 3.1

Let M be a graded left A -module. Then we have the following equivalences :

1. All nonempty set of submodules of M , contains a maximal element ;
2. all increase sequence of submodules of M is stationary.

Proof

Assume that all nonempty set of submodules of M , contains a maximal element.

We consider the increase sequence $N_1 \subset N_2 \subset N_3 \subset \dots$ of submodules of M . Then the family $(N_n)_{n>0}$ contains a maximal element N_p , so, for all $n \geq p$, we have $N_s = N_p$, hence $(N_n)_{n>1}$ is stationary.

Reciprocally, assume that all increase sequence of submodule of M is stationary, we consider Λ nonempty set of submodules of M . Suppose that, by contradiction Λ doesn't contain a maximal element, thus if $N \in \Lambda$, then it exists $N' \in \Lambda$ such that $N \subset N'$. hence, we can build an increase sequence $N_1 \subset N_2 \subset N_3 \dots$ of submodules of Λ non stationarily of Λ . This is a contradiction.

Définitions 3.4

Let M be a graded left A -module with verifies one of conditions of Theorem(3.1) is said to be noetherian

Théorème 3.2

Let M a graded left A -module. Then we have the following equivalences :

1. All nonempty set of submodules of M contains a minimal element.
2. All decrease sequence of submodules of M is stationary.

Définitions 3.5

Let M a graded left A -module which one of conditions of Theorem(3.2) is said to be artinian.

Définitions 3.6

Let M be graded left module, M_* the associate graded complex of M . Then M_* is said to be noetherian (respectively artinian) if for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $M(n)$ is noetherian (respectively artinian).

Théorème 3.3

Let M a graded left module, M_* the associate graded complex of M . Then M_* is noetherian if, and only, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, all submodule of $M(n)$ is finitely generated.

Proof

M_* is noetherian, if for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $M(n)$ is noetherian. Since $M(n)$ noetherian is equivalent to $M(n)$ is finitely generated is verified in the category $AGr(A - Mod)$.

Proposition 3.3

Let M a graded left A -module and M_* the associated complex à M . Then :

1. If M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian) then M_* is strongly hopfian ;
2. If M_* is strongly hopfian, then M_* is hopfian.

Proof

1. Suppose that M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian), then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $M(n)$ is noetherian (resp. artinian) so, it exists $n \geq 1$ such that $ker f^k(n) = ker f^{k+1}(n) \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$, hence M_* is strongly hopfian.
2. Suppose that M_* is strongly hopfian, let f_* an epimorphism of M_* . Then, it exists $k \geq 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $ker^k(n) = ker f^{k+1}(n)$. Let $x \in M(n)$ such that $f(n)(x) = 0$; since $f(n)$ is an epimorphism, then $f^k(n)$ is an epimorphism, therefore it exists $y \in M(n)$ such that $x = f^k(n)(y) \implies 0 = f^{k+1}(n)(y)$. Thus, $y \in ker f^{n+1} = ker f^k(n)$. Then $x = 0$ and $f(n)$ is a monomorphism for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, so f_* is an automorphism, M_* is hopfian.

Proposition 3.4

Let M a graded left A -module and M_* the associate complex of M and N a submodule of M et N_* invariant fully in M_* . Then : If N_* and M_*/N_* are strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian.

Proof

Let f_* an endomorphism of M_* and N_* a fully invariant subcomplex of M_* . Then, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $f(n)(N) \subset M(n)$ and $f(n)$ induces two endomorphisms $f_1(n)$ of $N(n)$ and $\bar{f}(n)$ of $M(n)/N(n)$ such that the following diagram commutes :

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 N(n) & \xrightarrow{i(n)} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{\pi(n)} & M(n)/N(n) \\
 f_1(n) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & \bar{f}(n) \downarrow \\
 N(n) & \xrightarrow{i(n)} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{\pi(n)} & M(n)/N(n)
 \end{array}$$

If N_* and M_*/N_* are strongly hopfian, then it exists $s \geq 1$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $ker \bar{f}^k(n) = ker \bar{f}^s(n)$ and that $ker f_1(n) = ker f_1(s)$ for all $k \geq s$. Let $x \in ker f^{2s+1}(n)$,

then $f^{2s+1}(n+1)(x) = 0 \in N(n)$ thus $\bar{f}^{2s+1}(n)(\bar{x}) = \bar{0}$ this implies that $\bar{x} \in \ker \bar{f}^{2s+1}(n) = \ker \bar{f}^n(s)$, and so $\bar{f}^s(n)(\bar{x}) = \bar{0}$, ie, $y = f^s(n)(x) \in N(n)$. Since $f^{s+1}(n)(y) = 0$, therefore $y \in \ker f_1^{s+1}(n) = \ker f_1^{2s}(n)$. Hence, $\ker f^{2s+1}(n) = \ker f^{2s}(n)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. Thus M_* is strongly hopfian.

Proposition 3.5

Let M a graded left A -module, N a submodule and M_* the associate complex to M . if M_*/N_* is strongly hopfian, then M_* is strongly hopfian.

Proof

Assume on the contrary that M_* is not strongly hopfian, then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ it exists $f \in \text{end}(M(n))$ such that $\ker f^k(n) \neq \ker f^{k+1}(n+1)$ for all $k \geq 1$. In particular, $f(n)$ is not a monomorphism, thus $N = \ker f(n) \neq 0$. $f(n)$ induces an endomorphism $\bar{f}(n)$ of $M(n)/N(n)$ such that $\bar{f}(n)(\bar{x}) = \overline{f(n)(x)}$. By hypothesis, $M(n)/N(n)$ is strongly hopfian for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, so it exists $m \geq 1$ such that $\ker \bar{f}^m(n) = \ker \bar{f}^k(n)$ for all $k \geq m$. Let $x \in \ker f^{m+2}(n)$, then $\bar{x} \in \ker \bar{f}^{m+2}(n) = \ker \bar{f}^m(n)$ this implies that $f^m(n)(x) \in N(n)$. Hence $f(n)(f^m(n)(x) = 0$ ie., $x \in \ker f^{m+1}(n)$. Therefore, we have $\ker f^{m+1}(n) \neq \ker f^{m+2}(n)$ this contradicting the no stationary of the sequence $\ker f(n) \subset \ker f^2(n) \subset \dots$. We deduce that $M(n)$ is strongly hopfian, so M_* is strongly hopfian.

4 Strongly cohopfian objects in the catégories $AGr(A - Mod)$ and $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$

Définitions 4.1

Let M_* be an object of $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of $M_* :$

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \\ & & f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & f(n-1) \downarrow \\ M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \end{array}$$

Then the chain complex

$$(Im f_*^k) : \dots \rightarrow Im f_*^k(n+1) \xrightarrow{\delta_{n+1}^k} Im f_*^k(n) \xrightarrow{\delta_n^k} Im f_*^k(n-1) \xrightarrow{\delta_{n-1}^k} \dots$$

is stationary if, and only if, it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that $(Im f_*^{k_0}) = (Im f_*^{k_0+s})$ for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proposition 4.1

Let M_* be an object of $COMP(AGr(A - Mod))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of $M_* :$

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \\ & & f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & f(n-1) \downarrow \\ M_* : \dots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \dots \end{array}$$

Given $\delta^k(n+1) : Im f^k(n+1) \longrightarrow Im f^k(n)$

$x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$

where $f^k(n+1) = f(n+1) \circ f(n+1) \circ \dots \circ f(n+1)$, with k factors, then $\delta^k(n+1)$ is the induced morphism by $\delta^{k+1}(n+1)$.

Proof

Considering $\delta^k(n + 1) : \text{Im}f^k(n + 1) \longrightarrow \text{Im}f^k(n)$

$$x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$$

and $\delta^k(n + 1) : \text{Im}f^{k+1}(n + 1) \longrightarrow \text{Im}f^{k+1}(n)$

$$x \longmapsto d_{n+1}(x)$$

We obtain $\text{Im}f^{k+1}(n+1) \subset \text{Im}f^k(n+1)$ and $\text{Im}f^{k+1}(n) \subset \text{Im}f^k(n)$, therefore $\delta^{k+1}(n+1)$ is the morphism induced by δ_{n+1}^k .

Proposition 4.2

Let M_* be an object of $\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* :

$$\begin{array}{ccccccccccc} M_* : \cdots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \cdots \\ f_* \downarrow & & f(n+1) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & f(n-1) \downarrow & & \\ M_* : \cdots & \longrightarrow & M(n+1) & \xrightarrow{d_{n+1}} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{d_n} & M(n-1) & \longrightarrow & \cdots \end{array}$$

Then $(\text{Im}f_*^k)$ is stationary if, and only if, $(\text{Im}f^k(n))$ stabilizes for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$

Proof

If $(\text{Im}f_*^k)$ is stationary, then it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that $(\text{Im}f_*^k) = (\text{Im}f_*^{k+s})$, for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$, hence $\text{Im}f^{k_0}(n) = \text{Im}f^{k_0+s}(n)$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. This implies that $(\text{Im}f^k(n))$ stabilizes for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Reciprocally, assume that $(\text{Im}f^k(n))$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, then it exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$ then $\text{Im}f^{k_0}(n) = \text{Im}f^{k_0+s}(n)$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.

So $(\text{Im}f_*^k)$ is stationary for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$

Définitions 4.2

Let M_* be an object of $\text{COMP}(\text{AGr}(A - \text{Mod}))$ and f_* a complex endomorphism of M_* . M_* is said to be strongly cohopfian, if for any endomorphism f_* of M_* , $(\text{Im}f_*^k)$ is stationary.

Proposition 4.3

Let M a graded left A -module and M_* the associated complex à M . Then :

1. If M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian) then M_* is strongly cohopfian ;
2. If M_* is strongly cohopfian, then M_* is cohopfian.

Proof

1. Suppose that M_* is noetherian (resp. artinian), then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $M(n)$ is noetherian (resp. artinian) so, it exists $n \geq 1$ such that $\text{Im}f^k(n) = \text{Im}f^{k+1}(n) \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$, hence M_* is strongly cohopfian.
2. Suppose that M_* is strongly cohopfian, let f_* a monomorphism of M_* . Then, it exists $k \geq 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\text{Im}f^k(n) = \text{Im}f^{k+1}(n)$, since $f(n)$ is injective, then $f^k(n)$ is injective. Let $x \in M(n)$, it exists $y \in M(n)$ such that $f^k(n)(x) = f^{k+1}(n)(y)$. Thus, $x - f(n)(y) \in \ker f^k(n) = 0$. Hence $x = f(n)(y)$, therefore $f(n) \in \text{Aut}(M(n))$, this equivalent to f_* is an automorphism of M_* .

Proposition 4.4

Let M a graded left A -module and M_* the associate complex of M and N a submodule of M et N_* invariant fully in M_* . Then : If N_* and M_*/N_* are strongly cohopfians, then M_* is strongly cohopfian.

Prove

Let f_* an endomorphism of M_* and N_* a fully invariant subcomplex of M_* . Then, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $f(n)(N) \subset M(n)$ and $f(n)$ induces two endomorphisms $f_1(n)$ of $N(n)$ and $\bar{f}(n)$ of $M(n)/N(n)$ such that the following diagram commutes :

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 N(n) & \xrightarrow{i(n)} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{\pi(n)} & M(n)/N(n) \\
 f_1(n) \downarrow & & f(n) \downarrow & & \bar{f}(n) \downarrow \\
 N(n) & \xrightarrow{i(n)} & M(n) & \xrightarrow{\pi(n)} & M(n)/N(n)
 \end{array}$$

If N_* and M_*/N_* are strongly cohopfian, then it exists $s \geq 1$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $\bar{f}^k(n)(M(n)/N(n)) = \bar{f}^s(n)(M(n)/N(n))$. Again, it exists $m \geq 1$ such that $f_1^k(n)(N(n)) = f_1^m(n)(N(n))$ for all $k \geq m$. Put $p = s + m$. For each $x \in M(n)$, we have $\bar{f}^s(n)(\bar{x}) = \bar{f}^{s+1}(n)(\bar{y})$ for some $y \in M(n)$. This implies $t = f^s(n)(x) - f^{s+1}(n)(y) \in N(n)$. Hence $f^m(n)(t) = f_1^{p+1}(z)$, for some $z \in N(n)$. It becomes that $f^p(n)(x) = f^{p+1}(n)(y + z)$, hence $\text{Im} f^p(n) = \text{Im} f^{p+1}(n)$. Therefore $M(n)$ is strongly cohopfian for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, so M_* is cohopfian.

Proposition 4.5

Let M a graded left A -module, N a submodule and M_* the associate complex to M . If all subcomplex of M_* is cohopfian, then M_* is cohopfian.

Proof

Suppose that M_* is not strongly cohopfian, then for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ it exists an endomorphism $f(n) \in \text{End}(M(n))$ such that $\text{Im} f^k(n) \neq \text{Im} f$ for all $k \geq 1$. In particular, $f(n)$ is not surjective, thus $N(n) = \text{Im} f(n)$ is an own submodule of $M(n)$. By hypothesis, $N(n)$ is strongly cohopfian, thus the endomorphism $g(n) = f(n)|_{N(n)}$ of $N(n)$, it exists $m \geq$ such that $\text{Im} g^k(n) = \text{Im} g^m(n)$ for all $n \geq m$. Let $x \in \text{Im} f^{m+1}(n)$, then it exists $y \in M(n)$ such that $x = f^{m+1}(n)(y) = f^m(n)(f(n)(y))$. Since $f(n)(y) \in N(n)$, thus $x \in \text{Im} g^m(n) = \text{Im} g^{2(m+1)}$, ie, it exists $z \in N(n)$ such that $x = g^{2(m+1)}(n)(z) = f^{2(m+1)}(n)(z)$. Therefore $\text{Im} f^{m+1}(n) = \text{Im} f^{2(m+1)}(n)$, contradicting the strongly cohopfian nature of M_* .

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